

Original Research

Modeling and Simulation of the Gasification of the Main Agricultural Wastes in Chad using Aspen Plus

Mbaiadjim Neatobeye Christian

Chemical Engineering, East China University of Science and Technology, 130 Meilong Rd, Xuhui District, Shanghai, 200231, China

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Correspondence:

Mbaiadjim Neatobeye Christian.
Chemical Engineering, East China
University of Science and Technology,
130 Meilong Rd, Xuhui District,
Shanghai, 200231, China. North
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Abstract

This paper presents the construction of a simulation model for the gasification of primary Chadian biomasses. The model is based on restricted chemical equilibrium in which temperature approaches were used as the correction factors. A sensitivity analysis was conducted based on the minimization of Gibbs free energy to ascertain the optimal flow rates of gasification agents. It was found that for a fixed mass flowrate of biomass of 40 ton/h, flowrates of oxygen in the range of 1170–15860 kg/h of oxygen and flowrates of steam in the range of 200–10500 kg/h maximized the hydrogen content in the final syngas. Similarly, it was found that final syngas composition is dependent on several parameters like moisture content, calorific value, and temperature, being the temperature the most important for which high values favored the content of hydrogen and carbon monoxide, and low values favored the content of carbon dioxide in the final syngas.

Keywords: Chadian Biomass, Gasification, Sensitivity Analysis, Aspen Plus.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, humanity has significant difficulty in identifying new energy sources to meet the rising global energy demand. The exhaustion of fossil fuel reserves and the detrimental environmental effects of carbon dioxide and greenhouse gas emissions are prompting a shift towards renewable energy sources, including solar photovoltaic, wind, and biomass. Chad is an African nation distinguished by its substantial biomass reserves derived from agricultural waste, primarily located in the Sahelian and Soudanian regions. Conversely, Chad experiences significant electricity service scarcity, which constrains economic development and diminishes the quality of life for its populace. Given this situation, the use of Chadian biomass as a renewable energy source for power generation presents an appealing alternative to meet Chad's energy demand and achieve the objective of reducing carbon dioxide and greenhouse gas emissions. The methods often employed to transform biomass into an appropriate energy source can be categorized as biochemical and thermochemical processes. Among these processes, thermochemical methods have demonstrated superiority due to their efficiency in biomass conversion, particularly gasification [5]. Gasification is a thermochemical conversion process that transforms carbonaceous materials such as coal, agricultural residues, municipal solid waste, and animal waste into a gaseous fuel called synthesis gas (syngas) in an oxygen-limited environment. Biomass gasification necessitates the utilization of a gasification agent, a material that engages in chemical interactions with biomass to generate syngas. The predominant gasification agents employed are air, oxygen, and steam; nevertheless, air gasification generates syngas with a substantial nitrogen content, which is undesirable in applications where syngas serve as a feedstock for chemical or energy production. In these instances, gasification using oxygen and steam is favored. The transformation of biomass into syngas transpires in multiple phases, with the initial phase being drying, during which the moisture content of the biomass is eliminated via evaporation. The second stage is pyrolysis, which involves the vaporization of volatile matter in biomass through the application of heat, resulting in the production of char, tar, and pyrolysis gas, primarily composed of carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, hydrogen, and methane. Tar is an undesirable byproduct as it diminishes the yield of final syngas; however, it can be further cracked at elevated temperatures to yield gaseous products. The third stage of the gasification process is combustion, involving chemical reactions between pyrolysis gas and oxygen, yielding water and carbon dioxide as products. This stage occurs at

temperatures between 700 and 1500 °C and serves as the energy source for the entire gasification process [7]. Aspen Plus is a simulation tool which has shown to be able to simulate the gasification process for given composition and mass flowrate of biomass and gasification agents. Several studies in literature have shown the capabilities of Aspen Plus to simulate gasification processes. Fernandez-Lopez et al. [8] carried out the simulation of the gasification of animal wastes using Aspen Plus. In their study, authors used a dual fluidized bed gasifier in which temperature and gasification agent/biomass ratio were varied using carbon dioxide and steam as gasification agents. The model was based on minimization of Gibbs energy approximation. Authors found that hydrogen and carbon monoxide production were favored at high temperatures and carbon dioxide and methane production were favored at low temperatures. Authors also found that when steam was used as gasification agent, the syngas produced were adequate for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis; on the other side, when carbon dioxide was used as gasification agent the final syngas was preferred as fuel due to its high calorific value. Rupesh et al. [9] investigated the effect of the addition of a sorbent to the gasification of saw dust using mixtures air-steam as the gasification agents. The model used was based in minimization of Gibbs energy. In their study, authors evaluated the variation of different parameters like temperature, sorbent to biomass ratio, steam to biomass ratio, and equivalence ratio on gasification. It was found that operating with sorbet to biomass ratio and equivalence to biomass ratio of 1 with an equivalence ratio of 0.25 and temperature of 900 K was possible to get a syngas with a composition of 31.1% of hydrogen which constituted an increase of 28% of its value in comparison with the case without sorbent.

Lan et al. [10] conducted the integration of biomass gasification with a gas turbine utilizing Aspen Plus. The authors initially simulated gasification and gas turbine processes separately before integrating them. The physical characteristics model utilized was RKS-BM, and the composition of the final syngas was determined via the minimization of Gibbs free energy. The gasification study assessed temperature and equivalence ratio, revealing that elevated temperatures enhanced the production of hydrogen and carbon monoxide while inhibiting carbon dioxide formation; conversely, the equivalence ratio diminished hydrogen and carbon monoxide output while augmenting carbon dioxide levels. Ultimately, the model for the gas turbine study successfully yielded the principal parameters of the turbine, rendering it dependable for subsequent research. Rao Pala et al. [11] performed a study on biomass gasification utilizing steam as the gasification agent and subsequently adjusted the syngas composition using Aspen Plus. The chosen physical property model was PR-BM, and the composition of the final syngas was derived using a corrected chemical equilibrium model utilizing temperature methods as the correction factor. Researchers discovered that the composition of syngas remained stable despite changes in the steam to biomass ratio, CO₂ conversion increased with temperature, and the H₂/CO ratio diminished as temperature rose. Upon comparison of the model's outputs with experimental data, it was determined that the hydrogen composition was overstated, while the methane composition was underestimated. Ultimately, of all the biomass examined, only the syngas derived from food waste was suitable for Fischer-Tropsch synthesis, whilst the other biomass types necessitated additional post-treatment with water gas shift reactors to modify their composition for compatibility with Fischer-Tropsch synthesis. The aim of the present study is to simulate the gasification of Chadian biomasses using the restricted chemical equilibrium approximation. The determination of correction factors in the form of temperatures approaches will be done through the calibration of the model with experimental data. The estimation of the optimum flowrates of gasification agents will be carried out through a sensitivity analysis, and finally, a comparison of the syngas composition results for each biomass will reveal the effect of biomass composition and gasification parameters on the desired results.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Aspen Plus Simulation Model

In this work, a simulation model was developed using the process simulator Aspen Plus V-11.0 which is presented in fig. 1 as follows:

Figure 2.1. Process flowsheet of the gasification model in Aspen Plus.

The creation of simulation model inside Aspen Plus involved a series of steps which include the specification of a simulation template, the selection of the components of the model, the selection of physical properties method, the

creation of a process flow diagram, the specification of feed streams to the model, the definition of operation conditions of each block, and the running of the model and visualization of results. Aspen Plus is a tool that operates in sequential-modular form, inside its interface the process flow diagram shown in fig. 1 was built using the simulation blocks available in the model pallet; further, these simulation blocks were linked using material streams and energy streams until its completion. The operation of the blocks in the simulation model obeys the following assumptions:

- Operation in steady state mode [1, 5, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18].
- The gasifier modelled is fluidized bed type [5, 15].
- Adiabatic operation [11, 18].
- The model is zero dimensions [14, 17].
- Operation at atmospheric pressure [9].
- Pressure drop is neglected [5, 10, 11, 12].
- Drying and Pyrolysis stages are instantaneous [5].
- Char is composed of unreacted coal and ash [5].
- Sulphur content of the biomass is converted to hydrogen sulphide [11, 14].
- Nitrogen content of the biomass is converted to ammonia [10, 14].
- Tar generation is neglected [11, 14, 16, 18].
- Methane is the only hydrocarbon produced in gasification [14].

The main feed to the process shown in fig. 1 consisted of the main agricultural wastes generated in Chad every year, for which information about its composition is available, and presented as follows:

Table 2.1. Proximate and ultimate analysis of the main Chadian biomasses.

Feedstock	Millet	Sorghum	Peanut	Maize cobs	Maize husks	Maize stalks	Sugarcane bagasse
Moisture	4.9	6.7	5.4	7.5	13.1	8.1	48.0
Ultimate analysis (wt.% dry basis)							
C	46.5	46.1	42.6	43.6	41.1	44.1	49.2
H	4.9	5.6	6.4	5.4	5.6	5.5	4.7
N	0.4	0.6	1.7	0.2	0.5	1.2	0.2
S	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.2
O	41.0	42.1	44.1	48.7	51.2	37.4	43.0
Proximate analysis (wt.% dry basis)							
Volatile	70.1	69.9	73.9	75.3	77.6	73.3	85.2
Fixed carbon	22.7	24.5	21.1	22.7	20.7	14.9	11.9
Ash	7.2	5.6	5.1	2.1	1.7	11.8	2.9
HHV (MJ/kg)	17.6	18.2	15.4	20.1	16.6	16.6	17.3
Reference	[19]	[19]	[20]	[21]	[21]	[22]	[23]

The main models used to predict the composition of synthesis gas derived from gasification, can be classified in kinetic models and chemical equilibrium models. Kinetic models are based in rate laws and approximated reactor models like CSTR and PFR [15, 16, 24, 25, 26]; on the other hand, chemical equilibrium models are based in minimization of free Gibbs energy, and provide information only about composition of the syngas produced without take into account the position in the gasifier [1, 2, 9, 10, 17, 18, 27]. In the present study, the chemical equilibrium model was used to predict the outlet composition of syngas for the gasification of the biomasses presented in table 1; however, this model was improved through the inclusion of restricted chemical equilibrium approximation, which is based in the addition of correction factors in the form of temperature approaches for the main reactions in the gasification process in order to reduce deviation of the model from experimental data [5, 8, 28]. The reactions used to restrict chemical equilibrium model are presented in table 2.

Table 2.2. Main reactions used to restrict chemical equilibrium.

Reaction Number	Reaction Scheme	Reaction Name	Heat of reaction (kJ/mol)
1	$C + \frac{1}{2}O_2 \rightarrow CO$	Incomplete combustion	-112
2	$CO + H_2O \leftrightarrow CO_2 + H_2$	Water gas shift reaction	+131
3	$C + CO_2 \rightarrow 2CO$	Boudouart reaction	+172
4	$C + 2H_2 \rightarrow CH_4$	Methanation reaction	-74

The restricted chemical equilibrium model was included in the simulation selecting the option “Restrict chemical equilibrium – specify temperature approach or reactions” in the Gibbs reactor block, which was realized using the block GASIF2 in fig. 1. The selection of this option allowed us to include the reactions presented in table 2 within an initial guess of the temperature approach for each reaction; this last parameter was further corrected with the inclusion of experimental data, which were used to enhance the accuracy of the model and get results closer to reality. The equation of state of Peng-Robinson with Boston-Mathias (PM-BM) modification was used as the physical properties model. The reason behind of this selection is that PR-BM include correction factors to take into account operation at elevated temperatures, which is the case of gasification, and is able to predict the behavior of non-polar or mildly polar gas mixtures like hydrocarbons and light gases as CO₂, H₂S, and H₂; using PR-BM, reliable results can be expected at all temperatures and pressures even at conditions closer to critical region [1, 4, 5, 11, 26].

2.2. Description of the Simulation Model

The process flow diagram of the gasification model is shown in fig. 1. BIOMASS stream, which represents the main feed to the process was fixed with a mass flowrate of 40 ton/h, this stream is sent to the reactor DECOMP where the pyrolysis of the biomass occurs, and the non-conventional components from the same added in the form of proximate analysis and ultimate analysis, are converted to conventional components. The yields of the block DECOMP are based in material balances and are calculated with the help of a calculator block. The heat stream Q-DECOMP represents the heat released by the biomass and is sent downstream to the Gibbs reactor GASIF1. The stream ELEMENT, leaving DECOMP block is sent to separator CSEP, where a fraction of 10% of fixed carbon present in the stream ELEMENT is separated, which does not participate in gasification reactions [14].

The stream TORNONEQ which represents the components that will be gasified is sent to the block RNONEQ, in this block occurs the conversion of nitrogen and Sulphur present in the stream TORNONEQ to ammonia and hydrogen sulfide; further, the stream TOGASSEP leaving the block RNONEQ is sent to the block GASSEP, where takes place the separation of ammonia and hydrogen sulfide from the rest of components that are going to be gasified. The stream NONEQ represents the components that do not participate in the chemical equilibrium, in this case ammonia and hydrogen sulfide; on the other hand, the stream TOGASIF1 leaving the block GASSEP is sent to the block GASIF1. The block GASIF1 corresponds to the process unit where occurs chemical equilibrium, here the conventional components coming upstream are converted to syngas components H₂, CO, CO₂, and CH₄ following the approximation of chemical equilibrium. The heat stream Q-DECOMP provides the energy required for the gasification reactions; similarly, in this unit the gasification agents, oxygen and steam, are input and its flowrates were varied through a sensitivity analysis to maximize the hydrogen content in the synthesis gas. The stream TOGASIF2, leaving block GASIF1, is sent to the block GASIF 2 where the composition of the syngas obtained from the block GASIF1 is corrected using restricted chemical equilibrium approximation.

Is suitable to point out that a specification required by block GASIF 2 is the operation temperature, which was taken from the stream TOGASIF2 with the help of a second calculator block and correspond to the equilibrium temperature obtained in block GASIF1. In this way, with the arrangement of blocks GASIF1 and GASIF2 is ensured that chemical equilibrium is achieved, and the composition of the synthesis gas is corrected to get results as close as possible to real gasification results. Finally, the stream TOASHSEP leaving the block GASIF2 is sent to the block ASHSEP, in this unit occurs the separation of solid components from gas, recovering a gas stream labeled as GAS constituted by the final synthesis gas, and a solid stream labeled as ASH constituted by unreacted char and ash.

The ASHSEP block corresponds to a cyclone separator, just this option was discarded in the simulation model due to missing information about particle size distribution of the biomasses used as main feed. By last, stream GAS leaving ASHSEP block is mixed with stream NONEQ in block MIX1 to include ammonia and hydrogen sulfide in the final synthesis gas; similarly, stream ASH is mixed with stream CFIX in the block MIX2 to get all solid products derived from gasification completing in this way the simulation model. A summary of the blocks used in the simulation is presented in table 3.

Table 2.3. Description of the blocks used in the simulation.

Block name	Aspen Plus name	Description
DECOMP	RYield	Yield reactor. Converts biomass components in the form of proximate and ultimate analysis into Aspen Plus conventional components
CSEP	Sep	Separator. Separates 10% of the fixed carbon from other components.
RNONEQ	RStoic	Stoichiometric reactor. Converts all the nitrogen and sulfur present in the pyrolysis gas into ammonia and hydrogen sulphide.
GASSEP	Sep	Separator. Separates ammonia and hydrogen sulphide from other components of the pyrolysis gas.
GASIF1	RGibbs	Equilibrium reactor. Compute the composition of the syngas according to minimization of free Gibbs energy.
GASIF2	RGibbs	Equilibrium reactor. Correct the composition of the syngas according to temperature approaches.
ASHSEP	Sep	Separator. Separates the solid components constituted by char and ash of final syngas.
MIX1	Mixer	Mixer. Mix the ammonia and hydrogen sulphide produced with the final syngas.
MIX2	Mixer	Mixer. Mix the ash and the total char produced in the gasification.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Validation of the Simulation Model

To verify the accuracy of the simulation model proposed, a comparison was made for equilibrium and restricted equilibrium approximations with experimental data provided by Gu et al. [29] for the gasification of rice straw and presented in tables 1 and 2 as follows.

Table 3.1. Comparison of syngas composition results for equilibrium model with experimental results.

ER	SBR	T (°C)	Equilibrium Model				Experimental Data			
			H2	CO	CO2	CH4	H2	CO	CO2	CH4
0.25	0.0	800	41.9	44.9	13.1	0.05	30.5	38.0	23.8	7.8
0.30	0.0	800	36.9	50.2	12.9	5·10 ⁻⁵	27.0	37.1	27.8	8.1
0.30	0.0	750	36.9	50.2	12.9	5·10 ⁻⁵	26.2	33.8	32.6	7.5
0.30	0.0	900	43.0	39.2	15.8	2.1	34.9	38.1	23.4	3.7
0.20	0.6	800	46.5	27.4	26.1	0.09	28.1	30.7	32.2	9.0
0.20	0.8	800	52.2	11.8	32.7	3.3	31.4	29.4	31.0	8.3

Table 3.2. Comparison of syngas composition results for equilibrium model with experimental results.

ER	SBR	T (°C)	Restricted Equilibrium Model				Experimental Data			
			H2	CO	CO2	CH4	H2	CO	CO2	CH4
0.25	0.0	800	31.1	37.2	23.0	8.7	30.5	38.0	23.8	7.8
0.30	0.0	800	28.5	34.8	28.5	8.3	27.0	37.1	27.8	8.1
0.30	0.0	750	25.2	35.8	30.6	8.4	26.2	33.8	32.6	7.5
0.30	0.0	900	33.0	34.6	29.0	3.4	34.9	38.1	23.4	3.7
0.20	0.6	800	29.6	29.4	31.4	9.6	28.1	30.7	32.2	9.0
0.20	0.8	800	33.9	26.6	27.9	11.6	31.4	29.4	31.0	8.3

As can be appreciated in table 1, exist remarkable differences between equilibrium model syngas compositions and experimental syngas compositions, this result is evidence that chemical equilibrium model is useful to give an approximated idea of syngas composition at outlet of the gasifier but is not able to forecast the real composition of syngas, especially for methane, for which the model was not able to predict its formation.

In the results presented in table 2, is possible to see that restricted equilibrium model gives very accurate results for syngas compositions when is compared with experimental data, this result is attributed to restricted chemical

equilibrium model uses experimental data as input and it allows to reduce the deviations between both values through the introduction of correction factors in the form of temperature approaches that allow to minimize the error; of course, the reduction of deviation is dependent of the chemical reactions used to restrict the model.

In addition to the results obtained for syngas composition, it was possible to get results for the temperature approaches used to restrict the model, which are presented in table 3 as follows:

Table 3.3. Results obtained for temperature approaches using restricted chemical equilibrium model.

ER	SBR	T (°C)	Chemical Reaction			
			Incomplete Combustion	WGS	Boudouart	Methanation
0.25	0.0	800	170	-7.09	-125.24	-256.66
0.30	0.0	800	170	68.48	-143.58	-269.47
0.30	0.0	750	100	331.79	-99.29	-241.75
0.30	0.0	900	100	500	-261.74	-319.43
0.20	0.6	800	164.83	500	-79.35	-410.21
0.20	0.8	800	170	465.61	-140.07	-350.73

As can be appreciated in table 3, for incomplete combustion reaction and water gas shift reaction (WGS) were obtained positive values for temperature approaches; on the other side, for Boudouart reaction and methanation reaction were obtained negative values. Positive values of temperature approach mean that chemical reaction is evaluated at a temperature above equilibrium temperature; similarly, negative values of temperature approach mean that chemical reaction is evaluated at a temperature below equilibrium temperature. Therefore, in our study, the restricted chemical equilibrium implied that incomplete combustion and methanation reactions were evaluated above equilibrium temperature and Boudouart and methanation reactions were evaluated below equilibrium temperature to minimize the error.

3.2. Sensitivity Analysis

To determine the mass flowrates of gasification agents to be used, a sensitivity analysis based in chemical equilibrium model was carried out, in which the mass flowrate and mole fraction of hydrogen produced was used as the optimization variable. The effect of each gasification agent on hydrogen production is described as follows

3.3. Effect of mass flowrate of oxygen on gasification

The effect of the variation of mass flowrate of oxygen on the mass flowrate of hydrogen produced for a fixed mass flowrate of biomass of 40 ton/h being processed is presented in fig. 1. As can be appreciated, for a mass flowrate of oxygen of 10300 kg/h the hydrogen mass flowrate in the syngas is maximum, with a value of 2190 kg/h produced for the millet. The value of mass flowrate of oxygen required is considered the optimum value. A similar behavior regarding to this optimum value was presented for the other Chadian biomasses whose results are summarized in fig. 7.

Figure 3.1. Effect of mass flowrate of oxygen on mass flowrate of hydrogen produced for the gasification of millet.

Figure 3.2. Effect of mass flowrate of oxygen on hydrogen mole fraction for the gasification of millet.

The effect of mass flowrate of oxygen on the mole fraction of hydrogen produced is shown in fig. 2. As can be appreciated, again a maximum value for the mole fraction of hydrogen with a value of 0.38 is obtained for a mass flowrate of oxygen of 10000 kg/h which is considered the optimum value. Although the optimum values with mass flowrate and mole fractions do not correspond, they are close each other; however, the optimum obtained for mass flowrate is the option chosen for our study due to represent the maximum amount of hydrogen that can be recovered from gasification with oxygen.

The effect of mass flowrate of oxygen on syngas composition is presented in fig. 3. As can be seen, mole fraction of methane decreases continuously with mass flowrate of oxygen, which is evidence that methanation reaction is unfavored with increasing of mass flowrate of oxygen. A similar behavior is seen as a mole fraction of carbon dioxide, this is evidence of occurrence of Boudouart reaction, which is also confirmed by the continuous increase in the mole fraction of carbon monoxide with oxygen mass flowrate. In the case of hydrogen, the maximum seen for its mole fraction indicates that WGS reaction is favored up to this point, in which reaction is equilibrated.

Figure 3.3. Effect of mass flowrate of oxygen on mole fraction of syngas components for the gasification of millet.

A further increase in the mass flowrate of oxygen causes that WGS reaction occurs in reverse form which leads to reduce the concentration of hydrogen in synthesis gas.

3.4. Effect of mass flowrate of Steam on gasification

The effect of the variation of mass flowrate of steam on mass flowrate of hydrogen produced for a fixed mass flowrate of biomass of 40 ton/h being processed is presented in fig. 4. As can be appreciated, the mass flowrate of hydrogen produced is directly proportional to the mass flowrate of steam being processed. Although this result seems to indicate that, increasing the mass flowrate of steam is possible to recover large amounts of hydrogen, the increase in mass flowrate of hydrogen produced is small in comparison with the amount of steam processed, in addition steam is an expensive resource; therefore, this result was the basis to discard mass flowrate of hydrogen as optimization variable with mass flowrate of steam.

Figure 3.4. Effect of mass flowrate of steam on mass flowrate of hydrogen produced for the gasification of millet.

Figure 3.5. Effect of mass flowrate of steam on mass flowrate of hydrogen produced for the gasification of millet.

In fig. 5 is presented the effect of mass flowrate of steam on gasification. As can be appreciated, for a mass flowrate of 10500 kg/h of steam the mole fraction of hydrogen is maximum, with a value of 0.3784. This maximum point for the mole fraction of hydrogen is considered the optimum value; in this way, the variable selected to optimize the mass flowrate of steam was the mole fraction of hydrogen produced.

Figure 3.6. Effect of mass flowrate of steam on mole fraction of syngas components for the gasification of millet.

The effect of mass flowrate of steam on the syngas composition is presented in fig. 6. As can be appreciated, methane concentration is reduced gradually with mass flowrate of steam, which confirm that methanation reaction is unfavored by mass flowrate of steam. A similar behavior is seen for carbon monoxide mole fraction, which is attributed to occurrence of combustion reactions; this fact also explains the continuous increase in the mole fraction of carbon dioxide and is due to the energy required by the gasification reactions to process the steam being added. In the case of hydrogen, again the maximum seen for its mole fraction is attributed to the occurrence of WGS reaction up to this point, in which the reaction is equilibrated. A further addition of steam causes WGS reactions in reverse way leading to the reduction in hydrogen concentration.

3.5. Comparison of Optimum Values and Syngas Compositions for Chadian Biomasses

The sensitivity analysis shown above for the millet was carried out for each of the seven Chadian biomasses described in previous section obtaining the following results for oxygen requirements.

Figure 3.7. Optimum values of mass flowrate of oxygen required for each biomass.

From the results presented in fig. 7 it is possible to appreciate that peanut and maize stalks were the biomass with higher oxygen requirements; followed by millet, sorghum, and maize husks; and maize cobs was the biomass with lower requirements. The high requirement of oxygen for maize stalks can be attributed to two factors. First is the biomass that presents the second higher value of moisture; therefore, in order to vaporize this moisture and reach equilibrium is required energy which is provided by combustion reactions that spend oxygen. The second factor is that maize stalks present the lower content of oxygen; therefore, due to the amount of oxygen is limited, the addition of oxygen from an external source for its gasification is expected. For the case of peanuts, it can be noted that it presents the lower heat of combustion; therefore, when peanuts are gasified additional energy is required which is added through combustion reactions that spend oxygen. The low requirement of oxygen for the maize cobs can be attributed to its calorific value, which is the highest among the biomasses studied. The high calorific value physically means that energy requirements from external sources are meaningfully reduced; therefore, the occurrence of combustion reactions decreases and hence the amount of oxygen required for its gasification is less. In a similar way to oxygen requirements, a study of the optimum values of the steam flowrate required for each biomass was carried out, whose results are presented as follows.

Figure 3.8. Optimum values of mass flowrate of steam required for each biomass.

From results presented in fig. 8 it is possible to appreciate that sugarcane bagasse and millet were the biomass with larger requirements of steam, followed by sorghum, maize stalks, peanut, maize cobs, and maize husks were the biomass with lesser requirements. From these results it is possible to note that there exists a direct correlation between the mass flowrate of steam required and the moisture and hydrogen content of the biomass. For the case of millet and sugarcane bagasse, were the biomasses with the lowest content of hydrogen; therefore, to increase the hydrogen content in the final syngas it was necessary to add hydrogen in the form of steam and increase its content through gasification reactions. Although the initial content of moisture of sugarcane bagasse is 48%, is suitable to point out that such value was reduced to 8% with the help of a dryer.

For the case of maize husks, its low requirement of steam is attributed to its high content of moisture, this moisture is converted to steam, which is further converted to hydrogen inside the gasifier. In the case of maize cobs, is also one of the biomasses with high content of moisture; similarly, peanut is the biomass with the higher content of hydrogen; therefore, the requirement of steam flowrate expected for its biomasses is low as can be verified in fig. 8.

The results for the gasification temperature of each biomass at optimal conditions are summarized in the fig. 9. Maize cobs present the highest gasification temperature followed by sorghum, and maize husks and peanuts present the lower temperatures. This result for gasification temperature can be attributed to two variables, the heat of combustion and the moisture content. Maize cobs present the highest heat of combustion followed by sorghum; therefore, the high gasification temperatures of these biomasses are attributed to its high heats of combustion.

Figure 3.9. Gasification temperature of each biomass for operation at optimal conditions.

Although maize husks present a heat of combustion comparable to maize stalks, its low gasification temperature is attributed to its moisture content, moisture requires energy for its vaporization; therefore, due to maize husks present the highest content of moisture, this moisture spent energy that led to a decreasing in gasification temperature. The low temperature presented by peanuts is attributed to this biomass presents the lower heat of combustion; therefore, a low gasification temperature in comparison with other biomasses is expected.

Figure 3.10. Syngas yield of each biomass for operation at optimal conditions.

Fig. 10 summarize the yields of syngas obtained for each biomass. As can be appreciated, millet, sorghum, peanut, and sugarcane bagasse were the biomasses that presented highest yields; on the other side, maize cobs, husk, and stalks were the biomasses with the lower yields being maize cobs the lowest. These results can be attributed to the amount of gasification agents required for its gasification. As presented in fig. 8 millet and sugarcane bagasse were the biomass that required the highest flowrates of steam; similarly, from fig. 7 it is also seen that these biomasses presented oxygen requirements relatively high; therefore, higher flowrates of gasification agents required are reflected in higher yield of syngas produced. For the case of maize cobs, fig. 7 and 8 is seen that it presents the lowest requirements of oxygen and syngas for its gasification; therefore, a low yield of syngas produced is expected as effectively is presented in fig. 10. Finally, a summary of the syngas compositions obtained using restricted chemical equilibrium model is presented in fig. 11 as follows.

Figure 3.11. Restricted chemical equilibrium syngas composition of each biomass at optimal gasification conditions. As can be seen in fig. 11, hydrogen composition vary in the range 16.81–35.70 being the highest for maize cobs and the lowest for maize husk, carbon monoxide composition vary in the range 18.95–32.52 being the highest for maize cobs and the lowest for maize husk, carbon dioxide composition vary in the range 19.60–51.60 being the highest for maize husk and the lowest for maize cobs, and methane composition vary in the range 11.78–13.56 being the highest for millet and the lowest for sorghum. From these results can be noted that main variable that influences the syngas composition is temperature, due to sorghum and maize cobs were the biomasses that presented the higher gasification temperatures and the higher molar percent of hydrogen and carbon monoxide; similarly, peanut and maize husk were the biomasses that presented the lower gasification temperatures and the higher molar percent of carbon dioxide. This last result is evidence that syngas composition is controlled by temperature, where high temperatures lead to syngas rich in hydrogen and carbon monoxide and poor in carbon dioxide; on the other side, low temperatures lead to syngas poor in hydrogen and carbon monoxide and rich in carbon dioxide. According to this result high gasification temperatures are preferred; however, it is suitable to point out that gasification temperature depends on several factors which include the heat of combustion of the biomass, moisture content, ultimate analysis, among others. Therefore, due to the interest in gasification is to get the highest possible content of hydrogen in the syngas, the cogasification of biomass with other sources that have a higher heat of combustion like coal or pet coke is recommended, in this way it is possible to reach higher gasification temperatures, hence increasing the hydrogen content of final syngas.

Conclusion

A simulation model for the gasification of primary biomasses in Chad was created using the Aspen Plus version 11.0 process simulator. The equation of state of PM-BM was utilized for the estimate of physical attributes. The model employed a constant biomass mass flow rate of 40 tons per hour, which was entered into the simulator utilizing proximate and ultimate analyses. The model incorporated various module blocks, including yield reactors, stoichiometric reactors, separators, Gibbs reactors, and mixers, facilitating the determination of the ultimate flow rate and composition of syngas produced given fixed flow rates of gasification agents. The model's outputs were fundamentally based on the reduction of free Gibbs energy; however, these outcomes were enhanced by incorporating experimental data as correction factors, which constrained chemical equilibrium to yield results more aligned with reality. A sensitivity analysis was conducted, grounded in the minimization of Gibbs energy, to ascertain the flow rates of gasification agents that optimize the hydrogen concentration in the synthesis gas. Oxygen flow rates between 1170 and 15860 kg/h and steam flow rates between 200 and 10500 kg/h were determined to be effective for this objective. Utilizing the optimal flow rates of gasification agents, the gasification model was implemented on seven Chadian biomasses, incorporating the appropriate temperature conditions for each biomass. Biomasses with reduced moisture content and elevated heating value attained the highest gasification temperatures; correspondingly, those biomasses that exhibited the highest temperatures produced the maximum mole fractions of hydrogen and carbon monoxide, alongside the minimum mole fractions of carbon dioxide in the resultant synthesis gas, which is an industry objective.

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